

**Archiving Dossier Narrative
La Sfera Challenge Project
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<https://lasferachallenge.wordpress.com/>

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Abstract

The archived documents were created for *La Sfera Challenge*, a digital transcription project in summer 2020. International teams of medieval scholars and paleographers transcribed unique manuscript copies of Goro Dati's *La Sfera* in two, two-week-long contests.

Project Contributors

The project included many people in different roles throughout the summer. Here is a compilation of the people who contributed to the project and their institutional affiliations (note that some people filled multiple roles in different phases of the project and are listed more than once):

Primary organizers

Benjamin Albritton
Laura Morreale

Participants: *La Sfera Challenge I*

Judges

Sara Carlstead Brumfield (Partner, Brumfield Labs, creators of FromThePage)
Deborah McGrady, PhD (Department of French, University of Virginia)
Brian Reilly, PhD (Department of Modern Languages and Literatures, Fordham University)

Équipe France

Team Lead: Régis Robineau (Portal Manager, Biblissima)

Team Lead: Emma Stanford (formerly of the Bodleian Libraries)

Team Lead: Anne McLaughlin (The Parker Library, Corpus Christi College)

Transcribers: Charlie Barranu (Oxford University), Carrie Beneš (New College of Florida), Laura Cleaver (University of London) Debora Dameri (Archivio Storico, Modena), Seb Falk (Cambridge University), Sarah Gilbert (Durham University) Stephanie J. Lahey (University of Victoria), Sigbjørn Sønnesyn (Durham University)

Squadra Italia

Team Lead: Paola Manoni (IT Services Coordinator, Vatican Apostolic Library)

Editor: Claudia Montuschi (Head of the Manuscripts Department of the Vatican Apostolic Library)

Transcribers: Maria Gabriella Critelli (Vatican Library), Elisabetta Caldelli (Biblioteca Vallicelliana), Sr Panagia Miola (Servants of the Lord and the Virgin of Matará), Pierre Chambert-Protat (Vatican Library), Vera Frantellizzi, Giulia De Simone, Maria Pia Cozza

Team USA

Team Lead: Laura Morreale (Independent Scholar)

Editor: Benjamin Albritton (Stanford University Libraries)

Transcribers: Raymond Clemens (Yale University Library), Marie Richards (Independent Historian), Christina Bruno (Fordham University), Caterina Agostini (Rutgers University), Rose McCandless (Ohio State University), Lisa Fagin Davis (Medieval Academy of America), Winston Black (Independent Scholar), Laura Ingallinella (Wellesley College)

Participants: *La Sfera Challenge II*

Judges:

Benjamin Albritton (Stanford University Libraries)

Lisa Fagin Davis (Medieval Academy of America)

Laura Morreale (Independent Scholar)

Team Yale

Team Lead: Caterina Agostini (Rutgers University)

Team Lead: Anne McLaughlin (The Parker Library, Corpus Christi College)

Transcribers: Lara Harwood-Ventura (McGill University), Aaron Macks, Harvard University), Debora Dameri (Archivio Storico del Comune di Modena), Valeria Federici (National Gallery of Art), Patricia Larash (Boston University Academy), Shana Worthen, Anna-Amicia Litwinska (Independent Scholar), James Freeman (Cambridge University Library)

Team Wellcome

Team Lead: Marie Richards (Independent Scholar)

Team Lead: Stephanie J. Lahey (University of Victoria)

Transcribers: Susanna Barsella (Fordham University), Francesco Ciabattoni (Georgetown University), Izzy DeSantis (The Ohio State University), Francesca Giannetti (Rutgers University), Jocelyn Karlan (I Tatti-Harvard), Rose McCandless (The Ohio State University), Louisa McKenzie (Warburg Institute), Paul Moffett (Memorial University of Newfoundland)

Team Spencer

Team Lead: Karen Severud Cook (Kenneth Spencer Research Library, University of Kansas)

Team Lead: Laura Ingallinella (Wellesley College)

Team Lead: N. Kivilcim Yavuz (Kenneth Spencer Research Library, University of Kansas)

Transcribers: Isabella Bolognese (Independent Scholar, Strasbourg), Marguerite Bordry (Université Sorbonne), Alyssa Granacki (Duke University), Sunny Harrison (Institute for Medieval Studies, University of Leeds), Liz Hebbard (Indiana University, Bloomington), Monica Keane (Special Collections and Archives, San José State University), Agnieszka Rec (Massachusetts Historical Society)

Team Vatican

Team Lead: Carrie Beneš (New College of Florida)

Team Lead: Winston Black (Independent Scholar)

Transcribers: Alexandra Amati (University of San Francisco), Alison Walker (Independent Scholar), Christine Kralik, Elena Brizio (Independent Scholar), Emily Graham (Stillwater,

OK), Matt Westerby (Washington, DC), Michael Ryan (Albuquerque, NM), Stacey Graham (Murfreesboro, TN)

Team Newberry

Team Lead: Isabella Magni (Rutgers University)

Team Lead: Suzanne Karr Schmidt (Newberry Library)

Transcribers: Erasmo Castellani (Duke University), Eva del Soldato (University of Pennsylvania), Daniela D'Eugenio (Vanderbilt University), Jesse Hurlbut (Independent Scholar), Sarah Iovan (Independent Scholar), Ilona Klein (Brigham Young University), Lia Markey (Newberry Library), Samantha Mattocci (Independent Scholar)

Financial and Institutional Support

Support for the project came from the IIF Consortium, FromThePage, and Stanford Libraries.

Narrative Section 1. Project Rationale and Scope

In an effort to confront the social isolation imposed by the global pandemic, this project created limited-term transcription teams to transcribe a different digitized IIF-compliant manuscript copy of Goro Dati's *La Sfera*, a short fifteenth-century text often written in a neat humanist hand and found in manuscript versions in several world-wide repositories. The transcription teams competed to determine which group could transcribe its version of the text most accurately, quickly, and cooperatively. The goals and results of the competition were threefold: 1. to introduce project participants to IIF and the FromThePage transcription platform, 2. to advertise this methodology to the larger community of scholars who work with manuscripts and 3. to demonstrate how transcribed texts, once complete, may be manipulated in the digital environment.

Procedure:

La Sfera Challenge had two separate competitions. *La Sfera Challenge I* took place between three teams from May 22-June 5, 2020, and *La Sfera Challenge II* took place between five teams from July 17-31, 2020. Each transcription team united around a different IIF-compliant *Sfera* manuscript. The versions used are listed below:

La Sfera Challenge I

Team USA, Yale University's Beinecke Library, MS 328, ff. 1r-24v

(<https://purl.stanford.edu/qp280dg5546>)

Equipe France, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Arsenal MS 8536, ff. 55r-78v

(<https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc80751f>) and

Squadra Italia, Vatican Library, Urb. Lat. 752, ff. 3r-26v

(https://digi.vatlib.it/view/MSS_Urb.lat.752).

La Sfera Challenge II

Team Yale, Yale Beinecke 946 (<https://brbl-dl.library.yale.edu/vufind/Record/3836488>)

Team Wellcome, Wellcome Library, MS 231,

(<https://wellcomelibrary.org/item/b19676724#?c=0&m=0&cs=0&cv=0&z=-0.5121%2C-0.0801%2C2.0242%2C1.6011>)

Team Spencer, University of Kansas, Kenneth Spencer Research Library, Pryce MS P4

(http://vm133.lib.berkeley.edu:8080/xtf3/search?rmode=digscript;smode=basic;docsPerPage=1;startDoc=1;fullview=yes;directlink=PryceMSP4_30)

Team Vatican, Vatican Library, Vat. Lat. 7612

(https://digi.vatlib.it/view/MSS_Vat.lat.7612)

Team Newberry, Newberry Library, VAULT slipcase Ayer MS map 1

(http://digcoll.newberry.org/#/item/nby_dig-13867)

Competition Rules:

Each team was composed of no more than 12 members, to include 10 transcriber/reviewers and 2 editors. At least one of the two editors was designated as team lead. Participants needed to sign up at least one day prior to the start of the competition and be approved as members by the team leader.

Each team needed to have at least one (virtual) participant meeting to establish standards and working methods. Successive meetings will be held at the discretion of the team lead. Each page had to be transcribed by one team member, reviewed by a second, and approved by one of the two editors before it would be considered complete. Dated transcription logs were included with each transcription submission.

The competition took place over the course of 2 weeks. *La Sfera Challenge I* was from 12:00 PM GMT Friday, May 1 to 12:00 PM GMT Friday May 15 and *La Sfera Challenge II* was from 12:00 PM GMT Friday, July 17 to 12:00 PM GMT Friday July 31. Teams that completed their transcriptions before the stated deadline were able submit their contributions when deemed complete.

Competition Criteria:

Transcriptions were judged by three criteria, in order of importance:

1. Accuracy
2. Speed
3. Team participation (those submissions that include participation from several members of the team will earn a higher ranking).

Only digital submissions were acceptable, and needed to include:

1. A link to the transcription,
2. A completed transcription log with names of transcribers, reviewers, and sign-off editors
3. A team page with at least 4 progress updates.
4. A witness-specific transcription guideline (see below)

Transcription guidelines were posted on the main website to help teams as they began to transcribe (i.e., suggested approaches to spelling, letter forms, capitalization, etc.), which can be reviewed at [OSF.IO/JFYUH](https://osf.io/JFYUH), listed as “Rules and Guidelines – La Sfera Challenge.pdf.” However, once transcription work has begun on any particular manuscript, the individual norms of the scribe dictate how the work should be transcribed. Therefore, each team produced a transcription guideline document for their manuscript with their final submissions.

Judging the Competition:

Judges were members of the IIF consortium, and the decision of the judges was final. For *La Sfera Challenge I*, Équipe France was awarded overall winner for the level of collaboration and accuracy of their transcription. There were also six other awards: Squadra Italia for “Too busy to compete, but finished first anyway;” Équipe France for “Best Conversationalists,” “Collaboration” and “Accuracy;” Team USA for “Best Trash Talk” and “Speed.” The results of *La Sfera Challenge II* remain to be announced as of August, 2020.

Narrative Section 2. Project Trajectory

The *La Sfera International Challenge* was styled as a crowd-sourced transcription competition to promote intellectual interaction and exchange during the period of physical distancing imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. Centered around Goro Dati’s text and bringing together three teams of roughly ten scholars apiece, the La Sfera Challenge charged each team with transcribing, within an allotted period of time, a different copy of Dati’s work held in three separate repositories. Over the course of the mandated two-week

period from May 22 until June 5, 2020, members of each of the three teams came together virtually to transcribe their assigned copy of the *La Sfera* text, then submit their digital transcription to a panel of three judges by the final day of the competition.

Team members were recruited from the organizers' professional networks, but also through an open call on social media circulated roughly ten days before the competition began. Within three days of publicizing the event, teams were filled, or nearly filled, with enthusiastic scholars, eager to come together around a text and engage in some timely, good-natured competition. More than thirty scholars participated in the *La Sfera International Challenge*, and many reported a high level of satisfaction with their experience.

The success of the initial planned contest, *La Sfera Challenge I*, led to the development and implementation of a second round of transcription with five more manuscript copies of *La Sfera*. Recruitment for the second session went more quickly, since the project had a significant amount of attention in the scholarly community. Moreover, many transcribers from *La Sfera I* were willing to return, to take over more responsibility, and to reach out to their own networks to engage fellow team members. *La Sfera II* was initially announced with only four teams. but shortly after *La Sfera II* was announced, employees of the Newberry Library reached out to Challenge organizers to ask if they could participate as a fifth team. Team Newberry was accepted, and the second session took place from July 17-31, 2020 with five teams in the competition. The level of participation was robust, with over fifty scholars active during the two-week period. As with the first iteration, participants reported on social media, both during and after the event, a very high level of satisfaction with the Challenge as it took place.

Both iterations of the contest used social media, especially Twitter, for outreach. As mentioned, participants were recruited through social networks before the challenges, but they also communicated their transcription progress, images of unique features of their manuscripts and links to blog posts on their team or institutional webpages. They used hashtags, #LaSferaChallenge and #LaSferaChallenge2, which ensured that members of the public and participants could follow the project. Using social media to create community among scholars has been one of the great successes of the project.

The transcriptions of all eight manuscripts created during the two interactions of the contest are proving to be very high quality. As a spur for innovative research, the project has already led to comparative examinations of the manuscripts (such as their physical features, scripts, and images), as well as discussions of the literary or historical features of the text (such as variants, meanings and authorship). The project will be the focus of a roundtable discussion, "Best Practices in Digital Collaborative Editing: A View from *La Sfera*" for the New Technologies and Renaissance Studies Series at the Renaissance Society of America Annual Meeting in 2021. See the proposal at OSF.IO/JFYUH, listed as "RSA_2021_Roundtable_Proposal_Best_Practices_in_Digital_Collaborative_Editing.pdf".

The long-term goals of the project are to create a scholarly edition of *La Sfera* (the last print edition was in 1865), as well as an English translation. Organizers are also gauging interest in a transcription challenge for another text, possibly in French instead, which would introduce the collaborative methods and technology to a different subset of medievalists.

Narrative Section 3. Project-Specific Digital Objects and Platforms

The website for the project was created in Wordpress Version 5.5, using the Rockfield theme. There are no installed plug-ins.

The manuscript transcriptions were created in FromThePage, using digitized manuscripts from eight different repositories.

Collaborative spreadsheets and documents for team use were created and shared in Google Docs.

Digital objects collected for the project include all project webpages (converted from HTML to .pdf) and associated documents provided by individual contributors, housed in the platform’s document library (in .pdf format).

A full collection of digital objects can be found in the persistent identifier DOI, at 10.17605/OSF.IO/JFYUH in the folder ‘Static Pages’

Narrative Section 4. Project Outcomes (including analytics)

Site analytics reveal that as of August 22, 2020, the project site has been viewed over 5,700 times. A geographic survey reveals a wide dispersal, with visitors coming from every inhabited continent.

[Fig. 1: Wordpress analytics for website as of Aug. 22, 2020]

Other planned outcomes include participation in a round table at the 2021 meeting of the Renaissance Society of America, and an English translation of one of the transcribed copies of *La Sfera*, to be published in an upcoming volume of *Italian Quarterly* (estimated for 2021).

Narrative Section 5. Documentation Statement

La Sfera Challenge has chosen the Attribution 4.0 International Creative Commons License. For more information [see this link](#).

Narrative Section 6: Project Bibliography

A full list of primary and secondary sources for this project can be found in the project PDF files located at the persistent identifier address, 10.17605/OSF.IO/JFYUH, listed as “Bibliography and Resources – La Sfera Challenge.pdf”